

PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

D5.1 Quality Assurance & Evaluation Report

Project Acronym	PRODIGEES
Project Title	<i>Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development</i>
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Abstract:

The PRODIGEES research and innovation quality assurance system has the objective to support the R&I quality and activities of the project. Agreed on by the Steering Committee, it is implemented with contributions from all consortium members. The instruments include feedback, revision, and in-house quality control for R&I publications in line with home and host institutions, the review of Secondment and Activity Reports, comments and monitoring reports of supervisors for ESR.

1. Quality Control for project implementation: Steering Committee and External Scientific Advisory Board

On the basis of the Coordination Team's preparations, the overall project progress and academic quality is monitored by the **Steering Committee**, to be constituted by at least one key staff member of every partner institution. To ensure close collaboration across geographical distance and time differences, the work of the Committee can take place with support from modern means of communication, including online meetings, e-mail, and telephone correspondence. The Committee will exchange views on the implementation and management of the project, timely realisation of activities, monitoring of secondments and activities, and providing guidance, evaluation and reporting as well as on specific problems that might emerge during the project implementation, with a view to jointly producing solutions. The discussions and decisions of the Committee will be reflected in regular reports of the project to identify potential challenges and assess progress towards the project's objectives and in view of the compliance with the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. All the decisions of the Committee will be taken with the condition of mutual agreement.

The PRODIGEES consortium will benefit from quality control, progress monitoring and advice by the **External Scientific Advisory Board**. The Board is composed of eight distinguished political practitioners and academics, who are experienced in managing international research projects and networks and who have comprehensive insights into the PRODIGEES focus areas. The inclusion of colleagues from countries (e.g. US and China) and disciplines (e.g. engineering and technology assessment) that are not part of the consortium, ensures a diverse and applied reflection on PRODIGEES work. Members of the External Scientific Advisory Board provide feedback to the Steering Group on an annual basis on the basis of full access to the documentation of the project. The Board contributes to the excellence of events and products, supports the dissemination and communication activities in further world regions, academic disciplines and sectors, and compiles, in consultation with the coordinator, a final evaluation report. The following distinguished scholars agreed to contribute to the work of the Board.

- Dr. Yu Dongxing, Assistant Research Fellow at *School of Open Learning and Education, East China Normal University, China*;
- Frederike Kalthener, Data Programme Lead, *Privacy International, London, UK*;
- Prof. Dr. Dirk Messner, Director of the *German Environment Agency*;
- Prof. Dr. Christof Paar, Founding Director of Max Planck Institute for Cybersecurity, Germany, professor at *University of Massachusetts, USA*, ERC Advanced Grant on Protection of IoT (EPoCH);
- Prof. Dr. Frank Pasquale, Professor of Law, *University of Maryland, USA*, (author of "The Black Box Society: The Secret Algorithms That Control Money and Information", Harvard University Press, 2015);
- Dr. Frank Tietze, Head of Innovation and Intellectual Property Management research group, Centre for Technology Management, *University of Cambridge, UK*, team leader of IP Models for Accelerating Sustainability Transitions (IPACST);
- Arun Sharma, Director, Direct Benefits Transfer Mission in Cabinet Secretariat, Government of India, is responsible for driving the world's largest identity (Aadhaar, India's unique digital ID) linked social benefits delivery program;
- Prof. Dr. Mahshid Sotoudeh, researcher at the *Institute of Technology Assessment (ITA)*, Austrian Academy of Sciences, associate professor for technology assessment and sustainability in Graz, Austria

Relevant Deliverables of the project include:

- D1.1 Minutes of the Steering Committee Meetings
- D5.2 External Scientific Advisory Board Meetings & Reports

D5.1 Quality Assurance and Evaluation Report

2. Evaluation of Secondments: Secondment Activity Report & Evaluation

Based on the preparations of the Coordinator, Steering Committee members monitor the successful implementation of research secondments. The assessment takes place on the basis of three elements:

- the Secondment Activity Reports, compiled by every participating R&I staff,
- an evaluation report to be completed by seconded R&I staff upon return from the secondments.

The evaluation report template will be made available online via www.surveymoz.com.

Relevant Deliverables of the project include:

- D1.1 Minutes of the Steering Committee
- D2.3 Secondment Activity Reports
- D5.4 Final Project Evaluation and Impact Report

3. Feedback, revision, and in-house quality control for R&I publications

During and after the secondments, PRODIGEES R&I staff produce publications for relevant research communities of sustainability and development studies, political science and international relations, law, sociology, economic, with links to technology assessment and related disciplines. The publications can take the form of scientific publications in academic journals or other formats, such as book contributions, blogs, concept papers, or policy briefs. They will primarily target peers, but also *multiplicators* like trainers, policy-makers and stakeholders from industry and technology developers. Scientific/academic journals serve as primary mediums to disseminate project results to relevant research communities through publications. To ensure maximum outreach, high-class research is planned to be submitted to recognised journals, e.g. *Journal of Development Studies* or *Internet Policy Review*, and publishers more known in the Global South (*Development Cooperation Review* or *China Quarterly of International Strategic Studies*). Results can thus be used by the communities as a basis for future research.

PRODIGEES foresees feedback, revision, and in-house quality control in line with home and host institutions for R&I publications. The quality assurance for R&I publications takes place in particular:

- a) In the framework of lectures, seminars and workshops, organised by researchers at home and host institutions, where they present and discuss their research with target students, researchers and local and invited external experts and interested public.
- b) In the framework of international scientific conferences, such as the *Global Development Conference*, *International Political Science Association*, *International Conference on Sustainable Development*, *European Association for the Study of Science and Technology*, or the *International Studies Association*, which serve as additional platforms for PRODIGEES researchers to present their research results to the international scientific community working in the field of sustainability. The consortium plans to apply for joint panels, and ESR and ER will be encouraged to make use of opportunities during and after secondments.
- c) In the framework of in-house quality control mechanisms of the researchers' sending institutions, including internal peer-review.

Before their publication as PRODIGEES deliverables, R&I publications are assessed and approved by the Work Package leaders or the Coordinator. Potential concerns related to the quality of individual publications and requests for revisions can be requested from the author of the publication and brought to the attention of the sending institution or the Steering Committee.

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Relevant Deliverables of the project include:

- D1.1 Minutes of the Steering Committee
- D2.1 R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society
- D2.2 R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society
- D3.1 R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment
- D3.2 R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment

4. Comments and monitoring reports of supervisors for Early Stage Researchers (ESR)

To facilitate individual skills development host institutions assign supervisors to Early Stage Researchers for mentoring and reviewing the career development plans of during the secondment. Supervisors provide feedback to the ESR on a regular basis, connect with the PhD supervisor at the hosting institution, and will encourage and guide ESR in publication processes, the participation in international conferences and in-house training provided by the hosting institution.

Relevant Deliverables of the project include:

- D2.1 R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society*
- D2.2 R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society*
- D3.1 R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment*
- D3.2 R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment*

* produced / organized / attended by Early Stage Researchers.

